

DIFFICULTIES OF TRANSLATION FROM ENGLISH TO OTHER LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This thesis studies the grammatical, typological, and genetic origin of English, Uzbek, and Russian languages, as well as the morphological, analytical, and synthetic characteristics of these languages. In addition, it also discusses the difficulties that arise in the process of translation between languages.

Keywords: morphological, synthetic, grammatical means, predicate, word-combinations, translation.

Every language features a specific system that differs from that of any others. This is often all the more so with reference to English, Uzbek, and Russian, whose grammatical systems are typologically and genetically heterogeneous. English and Russian belong to the Germanic and Slavonic groups respectively within the Indo-European family of languages. The Uzbek language patronizes the Turkish group of the Altaic family. Concerning the morphological type both English and Russian are inflected, though the previous is notable for its analytical character and therefore the latter for its synthetic character within the main, Uzbek is an agglutinative language.

As to grammar, the principal means of expression in languages possessing analytical character / English / is the order of words and use of function words / though all the four basic grammatical means – grammatical inflections, function

words, ordering, and intonation are found in any languages/. the opposite two means are of secondary importance.

The grammatical inflections are the principal means utilized in such languages as Russian and Uzbek, though the remainder of the grammatical means also are used but they're of less frequency than the grammatical inflections. The comparison of the subsequent examples will help for instance the difference between the language considered; *"The hunter killed the wolf Ovchi burini uldiridi Охотник убил волка.*

In English, the order of words is fixed. The model of straightforward declarative sentences in this language is as follows. SUBJECT - PREDICATE This means that the topic /S/ is placed within the first position /V/ - within the second position. If the predicate is expressed by a transitive verb form when within the third position, we discover the thing / O/ that is: S - Vtr - O Any violation of the order of the word brings a few changes or distortion of the meaning.

The corresponding Russian sentence adheres to the patterns S – Vtr – O. But it permits the transposition of the word i.e. Охотник убил волка Волка убил ОХОТНИК. 106 These patterns aren't equivalent. the primary allows transposition of words, which results in stylistic marking/characteristic of poetry/. Besides, the ending "NI" expresses a further meaning of definiteness. The second pattern doesn't tolerate the transposition of words.

The principal sorts of grammatical correspondence between two languages are as follows:

- a. complete correspondence
- b. partial correspondence
- c. absence of correspondence.

Complete morphological correspondence is observed when within the languages considered there are identical, grammatical categories with identical

particular meanings. altogether the three languages there's a syntactic category of number. Both the overall categorial and particular meanings are alike:

a. NUMBER SINGULAR PLURAL Such correspondence could also be called complete.

b. PARTIAL MORPHOLOGICAL CORRESPONDENCE is observed when within the languages examined there are grammatical categories ways identical categorial meanings but with some differences within the particular meanings.

In the languages considered, there's a syntactic category of case in nouns. Though the specific meaning is identical to altogether three languages the actual meanings are different both from the purpose of view of their number and therefore the meanings they express. English has 2 particular meanings while Uzbek and Russian have 6. Though the latter two languages have an equivalent quantity of particular cases, their meanings don't coincide. The differences within the case system or in the other grammatical categories are usually expressed by other means in languages.

c. ABSENCE OF MORPHOLOGICAL CORRESPONDENCE. The absence of morphological correspondence is observed when there are corresponding grammatical categories within the languages examined. As an example, in Uzbek, there's a syntactic category of possessiveness, which shows the affixation of things to at least one of the three grammatical persons, e.g.: Uzbek “Do‘st– im Do‘st – ing Do‘st – i” This syntactic category is neither found in English nor in Russian. These languages use pronouns for this purpose. English 107 Russian “*Моя моя подруга Your friend твоя подруга His / her friend его / её подруга*”.

In English we use certain grammatical means to precise particular and indefinite meanings, that's articles. But there are not any equivalent grammatical means in Uzbek and Russian. They use lexical or syntactic means to precise those meanings. / see substitution/ By complete syntactic correspondence is known as the conformity in structure and sequence of words in a word – combinations and sentences. Complete syntactic correspondence is never to be found within the languages examined here. However, the pattern adj +noun is employed in a word

–combination: red flags – qizil bayroklar, красные знамёна. an equivalent could also be said of sentences in cases when the predicate of the straightforward sentences is expressed by an intransitive verb: he laughed – u kuldi , он засмеялся.

Partial syntactic correspondence in word – combinations are known as conformity in meaning but discrepancy within the structure of phrase. Partial syntactic correspondence word- combinations are found in the following patterns.

Attributes are formed by the collocation of words. Owing to the very fact that English is poor in grammatical inflections, attributes are widely formed by means of mere collocation of words in accordance with the pattern N(1)+N(2) which expressed the subsequent sort of relations. Attributive English Uzbek Russian Glass – tube shisha- naycha стеклянная трубочка N (1) + N(2) N(1)+ N(2) ADJ + N The semantic function of predicative construction are often formulated as intercommunication and inter-conditionality of actions or states with different subjects. These constructions haven't any formal grammatical reference to most parts of sentences though there's always conformity between them. The degree of attendance of action or condition in predicative constructions determines the selection of complex, compound or simple in translation. Compare: I heard the door open... –Eshik ochilganini eshitdim, Я услышал как открылась дверь. In English sentences the predicative construction which functions as an object is composed of a noun within the common case and an infinitive. In Uzbek this construction corresponds to the word combination “eshik ochilganini” which carries out an equivalent function, though there's neither structural nor morphological conformity: it's a word combination expressed by a noun and participle.

Thus, an English predicative construction when translated into Uzbek gets nominalized. In Russian this construction is expressed by a posh sentence with a subordinate object clause.

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